

Business plan

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Work package 10 – Deliverable D10.8

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Summary

The Equal-Life project seeks to evaluate the impact of the environments in which European children are raised on their mental health and cognitive development from conception to young adulthood. The guidelines and tools developed in this project are designed for use by a variety of end-users, including researchers, policymakers, and practitioners. For optimal dissemination, collaboration between many different types of practitioners and decision-makers is ideally needed. This includes the people who shape public health and health care programs and policies. But it also includes the people who perform impact assessments, shape environments (urban planners) and influence programs and policies in a wide variety of other aspects of the public sector (including public health, education, housing, transportation, environment, urban planning and economic development), and in the non-profit and for-profit sectors (e.g., childcare, education, free time activities). Successfully addressing these dissemination challenges will require a combination of methods including communication outreach, marketing, advocacy, illustrated with successful examples, technical and training assistance, and enabling the adaptation of evidence-based models to new circumstances and their assessment. We make a distinction between profit and non-profit exploitation of the results of the project.

In separate reports we have provided an overview of all the different products of the Equal-Life project, and a dissemination strategy. These include the repository of Horizon2020 projects- Zenodo (https://zenodo.org/communities/equal_life) and the Equal-Life website ([Equal-Life website](#)) and the website where the tools are hosted (<https://www.equal-life-toolbox.eu/>). Potential users have been described in D10.7 which is also publicly available. Most of the products, metadata and data and codes of the project will be made publicly available and allow for non-commercial exploitation.

Of the different products which were described in detail in D10.6 four were identified as having potential to be commercially of interest. These include 1) The training protocols for the tools, 2) The biomarkers for mental health and 3) the innovative noise models, developed in Equal Life 4) Urban Analytics Tools.

The principal objective for exploitation in the Equal-Life project is to implement a strategy to facilitate the successful exploitation and adoption of results and benefits within public health initiatives, research communities and policy advisers. Exploitation activities in the Equal-Life project aim to ensure the longevity of the project's results through either policy uptake, further research or commercial applications.

This deliverable comprises the final plan for business and exploitation of results.

1. Introduction

Early life stage exposures to physical and social environments have a strong impact on mental health, cognitive development, and health inequalities later in life. The overall aim of Equal-Life project is to assess the developmental consequences of the environments European children grow up in for their mental health and cognitive development from conception to young adulthood. This will form the basis for improving unfavourable environments and development of supportive and restorative environments for children and adolescents. Consequently, Equal-Life will contribute significantly to reducing the burden of disease associated with mental health issues and cognitive development challenges.

- by providing insight in the key social and physical predictors of mental ill-health and cognitive development of children, based on the exposome approach;
- by linking exposures to biological and social indicators of mental ill-health and cognitive development;
- by better understanding the key mechanisms linking the exposome (internal, external, social) via intermediate effects (biomarkers) to a distinct set of outcomes symptoms, and diagnosed disorders);
- by laying a scientific base for a set of interventions improving children's health and cognitive development;
- by providing instructions for risk assessment of physical and social exposures associated with (mental) health and cognitive development of children;
- by delivering a toolkit for policymakers, urban planners, educational, social, environmental and health practitioners which will be publicly available;
- with guidance to identify, acquire and use the information needed to assess hazards, negative as well as beneficial exposures and the corresponding (mental) health risks and improvements in their given social context at local and/or national level; and
- access to information about implementation and good practice examples for interventions.

Key question is what the spin off could be of Equal-Life results and what the requirements are to do so in an effective and sustainable way. Companies that prepare spatial plans should include topics for children and topics on social, environmental and health aspects. However, this should be written in the legislation as guidelines may not be enough to implement the change.

2. Frameworks of action

To start giving an answer to these questions about spin-off and profit as well as non-profit users of the results we use the framework of action developed by Maibach et al (2007), see Figure 1, that describes the different fields of influence in the public health domain, based on a People & Places Framework. This framework describes the relevant attributes of people as operating in individual, social network, and community or population levels of analysis, and the relevant attributes of places as operating in local and distal levels of analysis.

This framework is well aligned with the ecological model of Bronfenbrenner, see Figure 2, and the approach we use of the fit of children and their environments from different perspectives as we described in the original proposal of Equal-Life. (van Kamp et al, 2022).

Figure 1: People and place framework (Maibach et al, 2007)¹

Figure 2: Bronfenbrenner's ecological model. Adapted by Joel Gibbs12

¹ Safety and perception should be added to community aspects

The organizations mentioned in the layer of the local and immediate environment, offer some good examples of stakeholders, profit as well as non-profit who could and would use our work. Within the ecological model this is the immediate family. Local environment refers to local level (Maibach) and the local environment, formal networks and services (Bronfenbrenner). Also policymakers representing the domains in the broader economic, policy, and other layers. These parties do not operate in isolation and a multidisciplinary effort is needed to develop any business case. These frameworks have the assumption in common that health is shaped in a complex interplay between factors which play a role in the interaction of a person/in our case young people from 0-21 and their physical and social environment. Understanding these processes could help identify the key stakeholders who are also the potential end users of our tools and in particular contributing to preventive action. Herby we should be aware that the end users mentioned in D10.7 are not necessarily those who will apply our tools and results. This includes a broad range of parties such as urban planners, social workers, (landscape) architects, acousticians, teachers, transport systems, cultural organisations, media, risk assessor.

The notion that processes at different scale levels play a role in human behaviour and health is not new and dates to more than a century ago. One of the key representatives from the social domain is Durkheim who commented: "The group thinks, feels and acts entirely differently from the way its members would if they were isolated. If therefore we begin by studying these members separately, we will understand nothing about what is taking place in the group". Even though Durkheim's work over a century ago illustrated the importance of population attributes on health (on mental health issues), the relevant attributes of groups, communities, and populations with regard to health behaviours and health are perhaps the least well understood thus far.

What we are trying to achieve here is to develop a business plan from a holistic point of view. The challenges we are confronted with in public health prevention were well worded by Maibach et al, 2007.

"Conceptually, the challenges are straight-forward: encouraging practitioners and policy makers to factor the evidence-base into their decision-making; and making it easy for them to effectively do so. To fully harness the value of the evidence-based public health paradigm, however, we must successfully address these dissemination challenges with many different types of practitioners and decision-makers. Most obviously, this includes the people who shape public health and health care programs and policies. But it also includes the people who influence programs and policies in a wide variety of other aspects of the public sector (including planning, education, housing, transportation, environment, and economic development), and in the non-profit and for-profit sectors (e.g., childcare, education, elder care). Successfully addressing these dissemination challenges will require a combination of methods including communication outreach, marketing, advocacy, illustrating with successful examples, technical assistance, and enabling the adaptation of evidence-based models to new circumstances."

Most of the steps described here fall outside the scope of this project. However, the Equal-Life tools and training protocol and the Guidebook explaining how to use them efficiently form the first step to include the evidence in planning and decision making.

2.1 Three 'E' Framework of intervention

A prominent framework for interdisciplinary work on interventions, for example, for improving health protection are the so-called 3 E's, Engineering, Education, Enforcement, typically used in road safety policy (Damon, 1958), but also in other fields, e.g., sustainability (Reames et al., 2020)). There are several extensions to the three E's, e.g. one of them being Engineering, Education, Enforcement, Engagement/Encouragement, and Evaluation (Evenson et al., 2023). Each of the E's form a pillar together underpinning the roof of a "temple of intervention". To the five pillars a sixth 'E' could be added (see Figure 3), namely considering 'Equity' and, thus, avoiding interventional inequity, as it is pointed out in Equal Life WP4. Enforcement stands for the setting of regulations/guidance to push forward the planning and constructing of a physical environment, healthy for children and young people and in combination with that the implementation of social programs or at least consideration of social (equity) issues in urban planning. Engineering points out the design of a physical and social environment beneficial for the children's mental health and their cognitive development. Education means training both the children and their families as well as the policy maker, planners, and researcher in addressing and dealing with both the physical and social exposure regarding children's mental health and cognitive development. Encouragement/engagement means the active involvement of children and families in co-designing their physical and social environment they are exposed to. For planners and policy makers this means, instead of designing for children moving to taking over the child's perspective and designing with the children.

Finally, Evaluation means, that efforts and results of interventional programs should be monitored and evaluated, both regarding the intervention process as well as outcomes.

The business plan includes consultancy and tools provided for each of the six pillars as outcomes of Equal life. A main issue is that all pillars are needed to stabilize the 'temple of intervention'. Thus, whereas one tool, one guideline developed in Equal Life may belong to one pillar and provided to the public mostly for open access, consultancy and training will be needed to bring them all together, for example when forming an interdisciplinary team on a local or national level with a comprehensive, combined action program (all under one 'roof'). This is exactly what follows at best the exposome approach where the focus as in Equal Life lies on the combined impact on children's mental health and cognitive development.

Figure 3: The 6 'E'-pillars of the 'temple of interdisciplinary intervention'

3. Economic impacts : Early intervention pays off

The field of epigenetics has demonstrated that genetic expression is strongly influenced by environmental influences – both at the physical and social level -and that environmental effects on gene expression can be inherited, rather than that they are genetically determined. Interventions at an early age thus might improve cognitive development and mental health and via these pathways positively affect inequalities at later life stages in an indirect way. The benefits of these interventions have been shown to outweigh the costs in the long term. Poorer self-regulation, as evidenced by greater difficulties with attentional control, delayed gratification, and inhibitory control has been associated with growing up in poverty.

in children, providing an eye-opening understanding that society invests too much money in later development when it is often too late to provide great value. It shows the economic benefits of investing early and building skill upon skill to provide greater success to more children and greater productivity and reduce social spending for society.

4. Expected impact of Equal-Life and related interventions

Mental disorders are notable contributors to the European burden of disease and accompanying costs. The increase of exposure to negative physical and social factors (,e.g. increasing levels of (ultra) fine particles, increased media use and environmental noise), the increasing loss of positive environmental factors (e.g. loss of green areal), and increasing social inequalities/inequity, is likely to affect child development and mental health in an adverse way, if preventive policies are not put in place. Many countries have recognized the need for action. This requires countries to develop capacities, allowing them to assess mental health and environmental and social risks associated with mental health, to make informed decisions about interventions. However, many countries are still lacking competencies, knowledge, tools and data to assess risks of mental health in the above-mentioned context, the field is still in an explorative phase.

The unique expected impact of Equal-Life is that the environments of youth 0-21 and time activities are described in a comprehensive way, combining social and physical aspects for locations relevant at different phases of their development. These descriptions and the sets of indicators that can be derived from it, form the base for the toolbox. This toolbox can be applied at different scale levels, and will be aimed at improving environments for young children in a more concrete and targeted way. The summary below describes the expected impacts and main achievements of Equal-Life and indicates which work packages are contribute to this. For a full overview of expected impacts we refer to the Equal-Life project proposal, Annex 1 part B (Page 52-55) and the technical reports of the project.

- External exposome assessment, new methods (WP1, 4, 3, 5)
- Internal exposome assessment linkage of new biomarkers to self-rated risk factors and external environmental exposures (WP2, Wp7)
- Data management: Large data sets on exposures or models to derive them (WP3,4,5, 6, 10)
- Enable researchers and policy makers to continuously include new knowledge in
- The policy making processes by using the toolbox to generate data and information, Interventions and good practices. (WP1, 5, 7, 9)
- Better prediction of disease risk by acquisition of new knowledge on the influence of external exposures on biological pathways at different life stages; Identification of early signs of health damage caused by environmental factors (WP6, WP7).

5. Products to be exploited

Table 6: Overview of the products in the Equal-Life toolbox

Type of product	WP/PI	comments	Location/requirements	Institute
I. META-DATA				
Equal-Life GUIDEBOOK	WP8/WP9 ZEUS		Open website , no restriction for access to cohort information-- Find function is included in the website	ZEUS QUANTIA
Overview of publications and public deliverables	WP10/all		Open website	RIVM
Overview of all (meta) data available in the tool box (fiches)	WP3/WP9/WP10		Open website	St George University, QUANTIA RIVM
Overview of all cohorts and school studies	WP7		Open website	Karolinska Institute
Overview of harmonized data and variables in each cohort	WP7		EHEN catalogue/Molgenis	Karolinska Institute QUANTIA
Overview of socially and equity-relevant community-level indicators	WP4		Open website	University Bremen
Overview of physical exposome data (indoor, outdoor, built, natural, lifestyle)	WP3 ULEIC, ISGlobal/GHENT, Tue/ WP5		Open website	ISGlobal St George University Technical University Eindhoven University Ghent Technical University Delft
Guidance to retrieve exposure data for specific locations	WP3, WP4, WP5		Open website	St George University University Bremen Delft University of Technology
New exposure data or models to obtain these derived in WP 3, 4 and 5	WP3, WP5		Open website	St George University University Bremen Delft University of Technology
Overview of interventions	WP7, WP8, WP9		Open website	Karolinska Institute RIVM
Case studies of equity impact	WP4 (WP7)		Open website	University Bremen Karolinska Institute

assessment of urban interventions /Good practice				
Conceptual models on mechanisms... (WP 1) and on the Social Exposome (WP4)	WP1/WP4		Open website	Gothenburg University University Bremen
Framework to consider equity aspects in urban interventions	WP4		Open website	University Bremen
II DATA				
Enriched data semi anonymized	WP3, wp5	- Access to AS can only be given with consent of the data owner within the consortium as well as outside the consortium	Zenodo	Cohort owners See table 5*
Aggregate statistics	WP6/WP7	- Access to AS can only be given with consent of the data owner within the consortium as well as outside the consortium	Zenodo	Cohort owners see table 5*
Pooled results	WP6/WP7	Access to pooled results only with consent of all data owners of data included in the pooled results	Zenodo	RIVM

Linkage between biomarkers and exposures (internal exposome).	WP2, and cohort owners	Biomarker determinants will be managed and shared by the responsible institutes and under their national regulations	Sharing with others is limited Finnian 12 data findable in https://thl.fi/en/research-and-development/thl-biobank/for-researchers	UEF IISPV Helsinki University
III CODES				
Codes enabling pooled data analyses	WP6 (in collaboration with WP7)		Zenodo	RIVM
Codes enabling data enrichment See also above New exposure data or models to obtain these derived in WP 3, 4 and 5	WP3, WP4, WP5		Zenodo	ISGlobal St George University Technical university Eindhoven University Ghent Delft University of Technology Bremen University

Most of these products will be free for use for everyone, and some for use after permission of the owners, in the case of the individual data. Some products are also eligible for commercial use. These include 1) The training protocols for the tools, 2) The biomarkers for mental health and 3) the innovative noise models, developed in Equal Life 4) the open-source urban analytics tools. These will be described in more detail below.

5.1 Training protocol for the tools

Training is one of the main elements mentioned by Maibach and of the “roof” in the 'temple of interdisciplinary intervention'. It is needed for successful dissemination of the results.

5.1.1 Training formats

Pilots

The first in-person trainings hosted to test the training setup and contents in a one-day session. Here, we piloted the programme, timing, contents (among others). This enabled an iterative process: learning from the experience of the pilots to optimize the trainings according to the stakeholders’ needs and therefore applicability of the toolbox.

Target audience: Local stakeholders from selected cities/countries.

In-person training sessions

In-person trainings are the most extensive form of the trainings hosted by the training team. These are one day trainings (some longer) similar to the pilot trainings, as these are further developed based on the learnings from the pilots. The in-person training are hosted in collaboration with EU city networks,

such as [Eurocities network](#) and the [WHO Healthy Cities network](#), as well as with partners from the consortium (Ljubljana context and Stockholm context).

Target audience: Local stakeholders from selected cities/countries.

Online trainings

An interactive webinar format series to introduce stakeholders to the Equal-Life project, its results and the toolbox. The goal is to raise awareness and understanding on the topic, to hold a dialogue on this knowledge and how it is related to the work of stakeholders in practice, the existence of the project & toolbox, as well as gaining momentum for future use of the toolbox.

Target audience: Broad audience, all stakeholders potentially interested & identified by WP8.

Language: These trainings are offered in the same format, but in different languages. This way, we can ensure that the context and interpretation of the information is as optimal as possible.

Programme:

1. **Inform** (session 1) on Equal-Life project and provide a general understanding of the exposome (approach), the general findings (to the extent possible) of how the exposome correlates with mental health and cognitive development in children.
2. **Reflect** from an exposome perspective on own work and context (session 2), and
3. **Introduce & demo** the Equal-Life toolbox (session 3)

5.1.2 Other formats:

Presentations at conferences and international events: several “light” trainings have been performed by the training team to inform various level stakeholders from different countries. E.g. during a Eurocities working group in Vienna, WHO Healthy Cities meeting and Green Economy Academy – Climate Change, Migration and Health (GEA-CCMH) in Cairo. These meetings presented opportunity for dissemination of the projects’ work, some preliminary results and the awareness and promotion of the toolbox and trainings that were ongoing.

Session 1: setting the stage & create understanding of the Exposome [related to mental health] Equal-Life as a project

Goal: Inform and showcase (definitions, scope, interconnectivity, demonstration)

To explain the Equal-Life project and to provide a basic but all-encompassing idea of 1) the exposome and 2) the general findings of how the exposome correlates with mental health and cognitive development in children.

Setting the stage is essential. What is the exposome? Why could it be important for you? How does Equal-Life play into this? Moreover: providing all the context needed to be informed as a stakeholder to start applying the exposome & mental health approach; state of the art results and insights from the project; basis to hold a discussion on the concepts within Equal-Life and to start a dialogue on these in practice.

Also including the following – explaining the project

- Equal-Life project
- Context of the project
- Explanation of most important concepts for people in practice
- Exposures important and available/considered in cohorts and in-depth studies

- Mediators
- Outcomes (in context!)
- Places important and available/considered in cohorts and in-depth studies
- Life stages of children
- Results of the analyses
- Key messages (so far), including results of other work packages
- Some higher level reflection on the process and interpretation of results (depending on stage of the project)

- **Session 2: Applying knowledge and tools to practice**

This session is highly dependent on the context of the training and the partners involved. Case studies will be discussed and explored from the exposome and mental health & cognitive development lens. (selected) Tools will be applied to provide the basis for this interactive group work. An open discussion will allow the participants and the team to reflect on, among others, ‘what do the Equal-Life insights mean in these cases?’, ‘How could they apply this to their own work?’, ‘How can we promote interdisciplinary work and implement the exposome approach?’.

Inspirationwalk: done in some trainings to “experience the exposome in real life” and discuss the experiences.

- **Session 3: Toolbox demonstration & exploration**

A video recording showcases the main buildup of the toolbox. A starting point to enter and explore the toolbox themselves. The time to explore differs depending on the type of training. This part of the training always ends with reflection on the (user) experience by the stakeholders, ideas and tips for further development and a discussion on how the toolbox can effectively be used and implemented in teams and by colleagues in practice.

Two Small Entreprises (Quantia dn Zeus) are partners in Equal-Life, and are well equipped to conduct webinars or trainings (online, in person) in applying the exposome approach in urban planning and/or health care services for children. Personnel from both SMEs would be interested and are well informed about the method and skilled to do so. The scientific results (e.g. RF results) and the tools developed by Equal-Life partners (road traffic model, SD metric, Delft tools, etc.) will be made publicly available scientific outcomes of Equal-Life. But, organising training and consultancies on how to apply the tools in practice could be commercially exploited and actually attractive also for non-profit stakeholders.

A tentative financial sustainability plan for trainings is presented in annex 1

Training and support

<p>Key Partners </p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Health institutes 2. Urban planners 3. International and National health associations as e.g. ISDE (International Society of Doctors for Environment), EPHA (European Public Health Alliance) 					
<p>Key Resources </p> <p>Online course (limited value) On site support for transitioning to a healthier environment</p>					
<p>Cost Structure </p> <p>Half day training with preparation for specific target audience: 1500 euro. Transition management: several k euro</p>					

5.2 Patent Mental Health Biomarkers

During Equal-Life analysis made it to the stage where initial potential biomarkers have been discovered. Now they would need to be validated using different cohorts and different methods. Once that is done, we would also need to carry out the following activities to determine whether the findings have commercial potential.

- feasibility studies and other studies related to intellectual property rights and the freedom to operate
- the examination of the research idea from the commercialization perspective (proof of relevance)
- the determination of the customer value, market surveys, customer studies
- the identification of competing solutions
- the experimental verification of the idea's viability (proof of concept)
- the identification of business models the protection of intellectual property rights to the idea (excluding maintenance costs)
- the identification of funding models and potential financiers
- Trademark costs are not eligible)
- communication related to the identification of potential customers and financiers
- commercialization and entrepreneurship skills coaching aimed to advance the project

In view of this it is too early to talk about a business plan for biomarkers. To be able to carry out the above activities, new funding and manpower would be needed, which is not available within the framework of the project.

5.3 Innovative noise models

5.3.1 SGUL

Modelling local traffic (i.e., minor or residential roads) to increase the density of traffic noise sources is an essential consideration for noise exposure assessment. More work should be done to improve the density of traffic models and extend traffic models to other areas, applying performance evaluation studies (i.e., comparing estimated and measured traffic counts) where possible. A large degree of exposure misclassification will occur without improved traffic data (flows and speeds). Furthermore, epidemiological research and health impact assessment should consider noise variability around dwellings (and not just the noisiest façade) to obtain a more representative exposure assessment.

Against this background City St George's, University London and University of Leicester developed a reproducible traffic flow model for noise modelling across Europe. The traffic flow prediction model was first validated in the UK, Spain and Denmark (see D3.2). Road traffic noise modelling (~500,000 dwellings) revealed significant exposure contrasts of up to 30 dB(A) between the loudest and quietest façades. It was investigated whether residents have "respite" zones from high noise levels. The exercise highlighted quality inconsistencies in OpenStreetMap road data for road traffic flow modelling and environmental noise modelling. The noise modelling was completed for all of the cohort and in-depth studies in Equal-Life (see D3.4).

5.3.2 UGhent

There is sufficient direct and indirect evidence to support the relevance of the sound environment when characterized using innovative traffic noise indicators—for mental health, well-being, and cognitive development. This warrants further exploration of the sleep disturbance index at both the least and most exposed façades of dwellings, as well as median or 90th percentile noise levels during the evening at these façades. Results are publicly available in D3.6.

The surrogate model that was developed in Equal Life allows to calculate these new indicators alongside classical ones approximately 100 times faster at the expense of 3 to 5 dBA imprecision on level indicators (evaluated in a different country as the one where the model was trained). The source code for running the model is openly available and a publication is under preparation.

Commercially there may be some value in supporting future use of the model and indicators by epidemiologists. Prior to generating commercial value by supporting environmental health policy makers, urban planner, etc., further proof of the value of the additional indicators is needed as well as software development for user friendliness.

5.3.3 Propagation models TU/e

Equal-Life noise modelling by TU Eindhoven has significantly advanced indoor noise exposure assessment by developing and validating analytical models that accurately predict indoor noise levels from outdoor sources (Terzakis,). The models enable the prediction of indoor noise exposure indicators based on existing outdoor noise exposure indicators (e.g. from noise maps) and features of the environment and building characteristics (e.g. as percentage of window area in the façade). The model was developed in WP3 of the project and has been reported in D3.7.

The developed calculation models are mostly of interest for research studies that aim to extend noise-exposure relationships towards noise-exposure relationships for indoor noise exposure due to environmental noise. The commercial value of the model is initially considered limited, as it is mainly of interest to researchers (epidemiologists) interested in indoor exposure. At a later stage, it may be of interest to urban planners and policy makers.

Models traffic and noise	<p>Key Partners </p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Researchers (epidemiology) 2. Urban planners 3. Noise experts 				
	<p>Key Resources </p> <p>Online business, proof-of-value (limited in Equal-Life)</p>				
<p>Cost Structure </p> <p>The only revenue could emerge from support for implementation <50k per project Thus, expected financial revenue is small</p>					

5.3.4 Urban Analytics tools (TUD)

The open-source Urban Analytics tools developed by TUD, such as the various components of the Data Collection & Enrichment tool detailed in Deliverables D5.7 and D5.8, have potential for commercial application, particularly within the context of the Equal-Life project. These tools facilitate the integration and analysis of diverse spatial and environmental datasets, enabling stakeholders to assess the impact of urban environments on children's mental health and cognitive development.

Commercializing these tools can follow a Software-as-a-Service (SaaS) model, providing subscription-based access to the various platforms tailored to the needs of public health and urban planning professionals. This approach allows for scalability and customization, ensuring that users have access to the latest features and models. Moreover, offering tailored training modules and support services can improve user proficiency and engagement.

To effectively bring these tools to market, collaboration with key stakeholders is essential. Partnerships with governmental agencies, research institutions, and non-profit organizations can facilitate data sharing, piloting, and the co-development of features that address specific community needs (e.g., identifying local accessibility barriers to play spaces). Engaging with these partners ensures that the tools remain relevant, user-friendly, and impactful in promoting children's mental health and cognitive development in urban settings.

Urban analytics tools

<p>Key Partners </p> <p>Urban planners, public health officials, educational administrators, non-profit organizations focused on children's well-being, and academic researchers.</p>				
	<p>Key Resources </p> <p>Online platforms for software access and support, workshops and training sessions, academic and industry conferences, and collaborative pilot projects.</p>			
<p>Cost Structure </p> <p>Subscription fees for SaaS offerings, grants and funding from research collaborations, fees for training and support services, and potential consultancy engagements.</p>				

6. Conclusion and future action

Most of the products of Equal-Life, including data, metadata, coding routines, and software tools of the project, will be made publicly available and allow for non-commercial exploitation. We identified four products that might be commercially exploitable in the future, namely 1) the training protocols focused on how to use the Equal-Life tools and included products in a sensible way, 2) the new mental health biomarkers to be patented 3) the novel transport/traffic and noise which were developed during the project and 4) the training module for the use of the open source Urban Analytics software tools. The specific parties who might be interested in the commercial exploitation of these products still need to be identified, but could be sought primarily at the municipal level, where it concerns noise modelling and the use of training protocols, and at the pharmaceutical industry end where it concerns mental health markers.

Regarding the Urban Analytics tools, relevant parties are the local public health and urban planning professionals, educational and research institutions, and non-profit organizations.

Additional/new funding is needed to further explore the potential spin-off of the project, both profit and non-profit which is not available within the framework of the project. A detailed financial and sustainability plan for the training is provided in Annex 1.

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Annex 1: Financial and Sustainability Plan for In-Person Trainings - Post-EU Project Model

Purpose of the Document

To define a self-sustaining, post-EU project model to offer in-person training days aimed at external clients (companies, public bodies, professionals), ensuring cost coverage and a profit margin.

Structure of a Typical Training Day

- **Duration:** 1 day (approx. 8 hours)
- **Delivery Team:**
 - 1 staff member from our company (coordination and technical support)
 - 2 trainers from project partners or external experts
- **Target audience:** paying participants (final users)
- **Modality:** in-person, at equipped locations

b) During the Equal-Life project, external trainers were not remunerated, only their costs were covered by the funding. However, in the commercial model after the project, they must be properly compensated. The cost of a single training day therefore includes:

- Fees for each trainer
- Board and lodging expenses, covered by the organizing company

Overview of Training Costs During the Equal-Life Project

c) The following are actual costs from in-person training sessions held during the EU-funded phase:

- **Cork**

Cost Type	Amount (€)
Internal costs	3,205.84
Partner costs	2,239.83
Service costs	1,691.83
Total	7,137.50

- **Amsterdam**

Cost Type	Amount (€)
Internal costs	2,778.86
Partner costs	535.70
Service costs	2,732.75
Total	6,047.31

- **Ljubljana + Vienna**

Cost Type	Amount (€)
Internal costs	1,455.15

Cost Type	Amount (€)
Partner costs	1,972.49
Service costs	1,717.50
Total	5,145.14

Estimated Costs per Training Day

Cost Item	Estimated Amount
Trainer fees (2 x €1,000)	€2,000
Board and lodging for trainers	€800
Internal staff (incl. meals/lodg)	€800
Venue + catering	€1,500
Organizational costs	€1,000
Travel and logistics	€1,000
Total	€7,100

Note: Costs may vary slightly depending on location and trainers involved, but €7,100 represents a realistic average in the post-project commercial model.

Proposed Commercial Model

- **Price per participant:** €800 (all-inclusive)
- **Break-even:** 9 participants (€800 x 9 = €7,200)
- **Optimal group size:** 10–12 participants

d) Examples:

Participants	Total Revenue	Gross Profit	Margin %
9	€7,200	€100	1.4%
10	€8,000	€900	12.7%
12	€9,600	€2,500	26.0%

Gross margin can be reinvested in:

- Marketing and promotion of future sessions
- Development and updating of training content
- Covering underbooked sessions

Annual Plan – Simulation

Training Days/Year	Avg. Participants	Total Revenue	Total Costs	Gross Profit
6	10	€48,000	€42,600	€5,400
12	10	€96,000	€85,200	€10,800
18	12	€172,800	€127,800	€45,000

